

MAGNETIC STUDY OF THE POLYMERISATION OF STYRENE.

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The magnetic study of the behaviour of styrene on polymerisation shows that the diamagnetic susceptibility goes on decreasing when the polymerisation occurs in vacuum, in presence of oxygen, on the other hand, the value falls slightly in the beginning and then rises, till after sixteen hours, it becomes greater than that of a sample polymerised in vacuum. The initial low value may be attributed to the intermediate formation of peroxides, usually of less diamagnetic character. The observed high susceptibility of polymerised styrene, which cannot be accounted for by Pascal's law, is regarded as the net result of the disappearance of double bonds in polymerisation and to its anisotropy.

Styrene polymerises to products of large molecular weights. The production of high polymers has been attributed by Whitby and Katz (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 1160) to the formation of a link between molecules by shifting a hydrogen atom along the chain. The formation of polystyrene according to this theory occurs as

The theory implies that the formation of the highly polymeric products occurs in steps, each corresponding to a specific compound capable of isolation as such. Such processes lead only to the formation of relatively low molecular products and never to high polymers.

The formation of really high polymers has been explained by Staudinger (*Ber.*, 1931, **64**, 2093; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, **32**, 104) by assuming that a molecule of the monomeric substance becomes activated and then reacts with a second molecule. The new molecule formed has active points on either of its ends and polymerises; this process continues to form high polymers. He represents the structure of polystyrene as

A long-chain polystyrene molecule is thus formed as a result of the disappearance of double bonds present in the original monomer.

In the present investigation the authors have undertaken to examine the process of polymerisation of styrene from the change in magnetic

properties which should take place if the disappearance of double bonds lead to polymerisation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Pure colourless styrene was prepared from cinnamic acid (*cf.* Roger Adam, "Organic Synthesis", 1928, Vol. VIII, p. 84).

Styrene was sealed in a number of evacuated pyrex glass tubes which were heated in an electrically regulated thermostat kept at $98^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$. After definite intervals of time a tube was taken out of the thermostat and cooled at room temperature, while the rest of the tubes were allowed to be heated further. The cooled tube was broken and the amount of polystyrene formed was determined by dissolving a known weight of the liquid in benzene, in which both the monomer and the polymer were soluble, and then precipitating the polymer from the solution by adding a large quantity of alcohol. After allowing to settle for some time it was filtered through a weighed sinter glass funnel, washed free from styrene with alcohol and dried in a steam oven.

The magnetic susceptibility of the cooled liquid was determined on a modified form of a Gouy's magnetic balance. Only the susceptibility of the liquids, heated for not more than 16 hours, could be determined, as those heated longer became too viscous to be transferred to the tube for measurements. It was found that reproducible result could be obtained only after great care. The mean values of several observations are tabulated below.

TABLE I.

Vacuum.

Time.	% Polystyrene.	Susceptibility $\times 10^7$.	Time.	% Polystyrene.	Susceptibility $\times 10^7$.
Original	0	-6.575	8 hr.	17.5	-6.937
2 hr.	4	-6.713	10	22.5	-6.993
4	8.6	-6.811	12	27.5	-7.044
5	...	-6.857	15	...	-7.105
6	13.2	-6.878	16	39.3	-7.112

Oxygen.

Original	0	-6.575	6	16.0	-6.436
2 hr.	5.2	-6.560	8	21.2	-6.787
4	10.7	-6.553			

While repeating the above experiments a set of tubes was found to be not completely evacuated but contained some air. The results thus obtained are embodied in Table I.

From the results shown above it is clear that in vacuum the susceptibility value goes on increasing with increased polymerisation, whereas in the presence of air, although the percentage of polymerisation is more than that in vacuum, yet the susceptibility falls slightly at first and then begins to rise. Also it is observed that with the increase in the duration of heating the difference between the susceptibilities of the liquid heated in vacuum and that heated in air goes on diminishing. It is possible that after prolonged heating, the susceptibility of the liquid heated in air may be more than that of the one heated in vacuum, but this could not be verified for the reason mentioned above. Therefore, in order to compare the behaviour of the polymerisation of styrene in air and in vacuum under similar conditions, the following experiment was arranged: Two tubes with the same pull on Gouy's balance were made and an equal amount of styrene was put in both. One of them was sealed in the presence of air and the other was sealed after evacuation. Both the tubes were heated in a thermostat for equal intervals of time and cooled to the room temperature and the pull was determined on a Gouy's balance. The results are stated below.

TABLE II.

Time.	Deflection in mg. per g. of the specimen.		Time.	Deflection in mg. per g. of the specimen.	
	Vacuum.	Oxygen.		Vacuum.	Oxygen.
Original	124.5	124.0	10 hr.	137.5	133.0
2 hr.	126.5	123.5	12	140.0	138.0
4	129.5	123.0	16	143.5	144.0
6	132.5	125.5	20	145.5	148.0
8	134.5	128.0			

DISCUSSION.

Staudinger (*loc. cit.*) represents the structure of polystyrene as a long-chain of styrene groups formed by end to end combination at the olefine double bond as follows:—

Much speculation, however, is rife as regards the indeterminateness of the formulae for polystyrene with free terminal valencies $-(\text{CHPh}-\text{CH}_2)_n-$. If the terminal valencies were free as suggested in the formula, the end carbons would behave like a free radical. From the magnetic standpoint the free radical should show strong paramagnetism and with the formation of a large number of polymers the diamagnetic susceptibility should fall, which is contrary to observation, because we find that with the increase in percentage of the polymers formed the diamagnetic susceptibility rises. It is therefore clear from the magnetic data that no free valency exists in the polymers.

Staudinger (*loc. cit.*) believes that as the process of polymerisation proceeds, an unknown side-reaction makes the free terminal valencies disappear. The first possibility is to suppose that ring formation occurs by the union of the two ends of the double chain.

Against this possibility there is not only the lack of experimental evidence, but the fact that since highly polymeric products are usually mixtures representing widely different degrees of polymerisation, it is necessary to believe that a large number of rings of different sizes are capable of formation with practically the same degree of ease. The second possibility is to suppose that the terminal valencies are satisfied by foreign elements or groups derived not from the parent substances but from the medium.

But the present investigation with pure styrene excludes such a possibility. Staudinger and Steinhöfer (*Annalen*, 1935, 517, 35) consider it more likely that a polymer contains a double bond at one end, the mechanism of its formation involving the wandering of a hydrogen atom from the end of one chain to saturate the end of another. The existence of such a double

bond has recently been shown by Whitby (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, **32**, 375) who found that polystyrene reacted with bromine. Moreover, he found that the amount of bromine that reacted with polystyrene corresponded to one double bond and the amount taken up was practically independent of the length of the polymer.

According to the last possibility, if n molecules of styrene, $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$, polymerise, the polymer would contain one double bond and in the course of polymerisation $(n-1)$ double bonds would disappear.

From the magnetic standpoint the constitutive correction factor value λ for an allyl group double bond in styrene is 4.51×10^{-6} . Therefore with the loss of one such bond the diamagnetic susceptibility of the product formed should rise by 4.51×10^{-6} units. When n molecules containing n allyl double bonds polymerise to form a polymer with only one such bond, the mass susceptibility of the polymer formed can be represented as

$$\chi = \frac{n\chi_s + (n-1)\lambda}{nM_s} \quad \dots (1)$$

where χ_s = molecular susceptibility of styrene, n = number of molecules of styrene which polymerise, λ = constitutive correction factor for an allyl group, M_s = mol. wt. of styrene.

If the whole of styrene were to polymerise to form polymers from 1000 molecules of styrene, the mass susceptibility of such a polymer according to equation (1) would be -0.701×10^{-6} , when the molecular susceptibility of styrene is taken to be -68.43×10^{-6} , and if 39.3% were to polymerise the susceptibility value of the solution of polystyrene in styrene would be -0.675×10^{-6} . Actually, as is given in Table I, the value of χ for liquid containing 39.3% of the polymer and the rest of the styrene is -0.711×10^{-6} . The observed value is much higher than the calculated one. It is, therefore, obvious that the magnetic change due to the disappearance of allyl double bonds only in the course of polymerisation cannot fully account for the observed higher diamagnetic susceptibility value of a polymerised product.

From the study of the double refraction of polystyrene, Signer (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, **32**, 296) concluded that on polymerisation styrene forms long chains of rod-shaped anisotropic molecules.

Experiments on magnetic birefringence of polystyrene have shown that a definite orientation of the polystyrene molecules prevails in a manner similar to that in the liquid crystals. This orientation has a two-fold effect on the value of the diamagnetic susceptibility. A first-order-effect arises from the fact that on account of the orientation in space not all directions

are equivalent and that therefore the mean value used in the derivation of the Langevin formula $x^2 + y^2 = \frac{2}{3}r^2$ does not hold good any longer, as a result of which the factor $2/3$ is to be replaced by something different. Another effect arises from the influence of the magnetic field on the electric moment of the oriented molecules which, although it is only of the second order, should be quite remarkable, since it is of the same type as the magnetic birefringence. Thus the observed susceptibility value is the net result of the magnetic changes due to the constitutional changes involved in the formation of polystyrene molecules and due to its anisotropy.

From Table II it is clear that the pull per gram for styrene heated in vacuum goes on increasing with the time of heating, but for styrene heated in presence of air, it slightly falls at first and then begins to rise and the value remains less than that for the sample heated in vacuum till the mass has been heated for 14 hours. After that the pull per gram for styrene heated in air is more than that heated in vacuum.

Staudinger and Lautensihläger (*Annalen*, 1931, 488, 1) have shown that the polymerisation products of styrene formed in the presence of oxygen always contain small amounts of peroxide. Thus when styrene is polymerised in presence of oxygen, two reactions, oxidation and polymerisation, proceed simultaneously. The effect of polymerisation on the magnetic susceptibility of the polymerised products would be to raise its diamagnetic susceptibility as has been shown by determining the susceptibility of styrene heated in vacuum, whereas the effect of the formation of peroxide is known in general to lower the susceptibility value.

Exact susceptibility values of the polymerised products could be determined theoretically, if the percentage of the peroxide formed were known and if its susceptibility could be determined. The peroxide has, however, not been isolated.

A slight fall in the pull per gram observed in the beginning on styrene, heated in the presence of air, suggests that the susceptibility of the peroxide is much lower than that of the polymer, but as the polymerisation proceeds and the magnetic effect due to polymerisation increases, the pull per gram goes on rising. After 14 hours, the pull per gram on styrene heated in air is much more than that on the sample heated in vacuum, because the percentage of polymerisation of styrene heated in air is much higher than that heated in vacuum.